

- 912الضفيرة كرمز و بنية سردية في رواية "الضفيرة" للكاتبة الفرنسية لتيسيا كولومباني
د. نسرین طه عبد الغني محمد
- 949التأثير الثقافي للمترجم على النص الهدف في رواية *Los Años de Fuga* للكاتب بلينيو أبولوس ميندوزا
السيد محمد واصل
- 973صورة الخلفاء الراشدين في الشعر الفارسي من المقدس إلى المدنس
د. الزبير الشلي
- 992البعد الانتقاعي للخطاب ومقصدية الممارسة الجدلية «رسالة الإغراب في جدل الإغراب»
سناء كوجان
- 1012استراتيجية القراءة والتأويل وممكنات النص (شرح التصائد السبع الطوال لأبي بكر محمد بن القاسم الأنباري " نموذجاً)
مولاي عبد المالك الباودي
- 1032التحول الرقمي وتجديد السياسات الثقافية: دراسة تحليلية في ضوء التجارب المعاصرة للمؤسسات الثقافية والتعليمية
ذة. وضیحة الجملي
د. منیر السرحانی
- 1046تعليمية اللغات في ضوء الإطار المرجعي الأوروبي: دراسة مقارنة بين اللغة الألمانية والعربية
حياة عبد اللوي
حسن بدوح (الأستاذ المشرف)

- 1069التخطيط اللغوي ودوره في حياة وتنمية اللغة العربية.....
أصلي فاطمة
د.منير بنرحال
- 1088خصوصية الحكاية الواقعية في المتخيل الشعبي شرق المغرب الأقصى.....
دة. حسناء بزغود
- 1101الهبة المؤدية لعدالة المدوح هي المهجنة على عقلية الشعراء.....
د. الزبير الشلي
- 1122صورة المعتمد بن عباد في الشعر الحديث.....
د. المعتمد الخراز
- 1168آليات قراءة النص الأدبي الرقمي.....
د.مها بنت عبدالله سعيد الزهراني

Transformation of Tradition in Contemporary Arab and Latin American Comics: A Comparative Study
of comics by Lutfi Zayed and Alberto Montt..... 1187

Marwa Muhammad Ibrahim

When Clarity is Not the Goal: The Challenges of Translating Political Ambiguity 1208

Nada Hashem El-Rawy Hassan

Between Hope and Resistance: A Comparative Study of Utopian and Dystopian Themes in Children's and Young Adult Literature 1217

Eisha AbdAllah Abdelkader Mohammed Askar

When Clarity is Not the Goal: The Challenges of Translating Political Ambiguity

Nada Hashem El-Rawy Hassan

PhD Candidate, Department of English Language and Literature, Faculty of Arts, Fayoum University

Fayoum, Egypt

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Abstract

Political language is a well-crafted language balancing persuasion, ambiguity and cultural nuances to have the greatest impact on the public, win their hearts, shape opinions, and, at times, keep things just vague enough to appeal to everyone. This paper takes a closer look at how political and diplomatic terms work, how ambiguity is used as a tool, and how numbers are transformed into convincing stories. The thesis studies the problems pertaining to the rendering of terminology presented in political speeches particularly the intentionally or unintentionally vagueness in them, trying to acquaint the translator with solutions to the problems that might face him when dealing with such material.

Keywords: Translation, politics, ambiguity, abstracts, and statistics.

المستخلص: -

اللغة السياسية لغة مُتقنة تُوازن بين الإقناع والغموض والفروق الثقافية، لتُحدث أكبر تأثيرٍ على الجمهور، ولتُكسب قلوبهم، وتُشكل آرائهم، وفي بعض الأحيان، تُبقي الأمور غامضةً بما يكفي لجذب الجميع. تُلقى هذه الورقة نظرةً على كيفية عمل المصطلحات السياسية والدبلوماسية، وكيف يُستخدم الغموض كأداة، وكيف تُحوّل الأرقام إلى قصص مُقنعة. تدرس هذه الأطروحة المشاكل المتعلقة بتقديم المصطلحات المُقدّمة في الخطب السياسية، ولا سيما الغموض المُتعمّد أو غير المُتعمّد فيها، مُحاولةً تعريف المُترجم بحلولٍ للمشكلات التي قد تُواجهه عند التعامل مع مثل هذه المواد.

الكلمات المفتاحية: الترجمة، السياسة، الغموض، المجرّدات، إحصائيات.

Introduction

A Glimpse into Political and Diplomatic Parlance:

'Political parlance' by which is meant the language, terminology, and style of communication adopted by politicians and diplomats in addressing the public, especially in mass media. Political parlance is a fundamental element of political and societal life. It is used by politicians, government officials, mass media and even by activists and non-governmental groups to communicate with the public and shape their opinions. This type of discourse basically used to express political points of views and to clarify social, economic and security issues, in addition to its role in directing pubic debates and political agendas.

Political parlance encompasses a wide range of tools, such as public speeches, press statements, interviews, parliamentary debates, discussions etc. Politicians use this language to literally form the public way of thinking about specific issues, downplay those issues' significance or even the other way around; i.e. to highlight them, which in turn would affect

the way the public is dealing with them. This means that the way information is presented to the public may be more impactful than the facts themselves.

For example, in times of political tensions or crisis, political discourse can be used to provide a calming message or to control feelings of anxiety and fear of the general public, as in Roosevelt's famous inauguration speech, in addition political parlance can be used to direct public support for government initiatives or to criticize opponents in politics.

Besides, political parlance plays a crucial role in political decision-making process, as government officials and leaders use it to explain their programs and policies, thus gain political support and legitimacy from the public. For example, politicians use speeches to justify their decisions about economic or foreign affairs policies, which in turn would convince the public of the necessity to make such decisions.

Political parlance is also connected with the Media as it is considered the main vessel or transmitter of it to the public, and it contributes to shaping how political messages are received and interpreted, as the media can raise or reduce the importance of a political discourse according to the agendas it adopts.

The power of Translation in Politics:

After reviewing the definition of political parlance and its importance in shaping public opinions and policies, it's important to clarify the role of translation in political contexts, especially between two main different languages such as Arabic and English, which are among the most widely spoken and important languages in the world. The first i.e. Arabic language is my mother tongue with deep roots in culture and history, while the second language i.e. English language is the global lingua franca, which is essential for communication and common understanding in all field, especially in politics. The significance of these particular languages is further emphasized by the political and economic power of the nations that use them.

Political rhetoric cannot be separated from translation, since the political interaction globally actually relies basically on the precise translation of the official documents and statements between varied countries. Translation in the political fields is not only about conveying words, furthermore it reflects the political position in addition to sensitive, complex and confidential messages. This of course makes it a crucial tool for promoting understanding, or even in particular cases or intendedly increasing the tension between countries.

Translation plays a significant and pivotal role in facilitating communication between different countries or cultures, this role can be seen particularly in political contexts where it is essential for the translator to be able to convey the meanings and contexts very clearly and accurately, in order to avoid any misunderstanding and to resolve conflicts. So, the ultimate fact here is that in today's interconnected and globalized world, political translation is a primary means for connecting different countries and societies, especially when speaking about two main languages such as Arabic and English, given the political and economic significance of the countries that speak these languages.

In politics, as I mentioned earlier, translation goes beyond conveying meanings from one language to the other, it also transmits the ideas, concepts and cultural connotations that may not be so clear in the original or source language. And we all know that in politics, political

speeches, official and governmental statements, international agreements and diplomatic documents etc. often have hidden meanings within words, as they may reflect complicated and sensitive political situations, or special historical and cultural connotations of the target language. So, when translating texts between two languages such as English and Arabic, for example, it is crucial for the translator to be fully aware of the political, cultural and religious reference of both languages, as Arabic, is known to have various expressions and rhetorical tools very rich with literary or religious references with very accurate meanings that not every translator, is able to convey to any other language, even if Arabic is his mother tongue. while on the other hand English language is known to be more direct and more idiomatic.

Bridging Politics across Arabic and English: Challenges and Solutions

There are many challenges that encounter translators when dealing with political material in Arabic and English languages. One of the most significant problems is the great cultural gap between the Arab world and English-speaking countries. For example, in Arabic political speeches the speaker may use religious or historical terminology that carries complex meanings, which can be challenging to convey accurately in English. Similarly, English texts may contain western legal or political concepts and idioms that have no direct equivalents in Arabic.

That's why in this paper I would like to shed the light on one of these challenges pertaining to the rendering of terminology presented in political speeches, trying to discuss the main ways that can assist the writer in dealing with political and diplomatic material.

Its also important to know at this stage that to use modern tools and techniques such as machine translation e.g. google translate and AI various applications can be useful in some contexts, but when it comes to political translation, it needs a human touch because of the sensitivity and complexity of these texts, since there is no room for mistakes when dealing with such material, as it can lead to serious consequences. In the International Translation Day in 2017, the United Nations recognizes the critical role of human translators "International Translation Day is meant as an opportunity to pay tribute to the work of language professionals, which plays an important role in bringing nations together, facilitating dialogue, understanding, and cooperation."

Between Arabic and English – and What's Between Their Lines

In the realm of political parlance, words are used as tools, chosen and crafted very carefully to inspire and persuade people, and sometimes even to deliberately obscure meanings. In that regard George Orwell, in his book *Politics and the English Language*, affirmed that political language is used to distort truth: "Political language... is designed to make lies sound truthful and murder respectable, and to give an appearance of solidity to pure wind" (Orwell 2021). Political language is sometimes used to mix truth with deception, through Vague meanings, whether ambiguous, ambivalent or abstract etc. This strategy is frequently employed by authoritarian governments. This is also can be further emphasized by the famous statement of Noam Chomsky in *Media Control: The Spectacular Achievements of Propaganda*, who spoke about the manipulation of political language in democratic societies pointing out: "Propaganda is to a democracy what the bludgeon is to a totalitarian state" (Chomsky 2011). This suggests that political language can be used for manipulation, much like power is abused in a totalitarian state.

Politicians employ this tactic, whether intentionally or unintentionally, by speaking in a way that sounds smart and powerful, employing full words and phrases that have weight. This strategy includes using specific words and expressions with less-than-precise meaning; these may be too general, too abstract, or too ambiguous to be safely translated into another language, especially when dealing with two distinct languages such as Arabic and English.

Politicians and the Appeal of "Fancy" Language

Politicians are usually attracted to specific terms and phrases that stir the emotions of the audience and excite them, such as "freedom," "prosperity," "justice," and "security" (الحرية) (الازدهار, العدالة, الأمن) which are commonly used in political speeches because they have universally positive connotations. These terms allow politicians to express shared values that are deeply appreciated by the audience, yet their meaning is also notably vague, or we can say 'flexible', as they can signify different things to different people.

This could be challenging for the translators to deal with, and to convey the meaning accurately. Let's take the term "Freedom" as an example, since it is a term with very strong positive connotations, with its Arabic translation as "الحرية". In Arabic it may have a 'spiritual' dimension as Arabic speaking audience may interpret it as a form of social or religious freedom, while the English-speaking audience might see it referring to political freedom or civil liberty.

Also, a notorious example is the one referred to once by Winston Churchill as a certain term to be consistently uncertain, namely to state that one's political plan is to achieve 'amelioration', that is to "affect an improvement" in whatever field one is working in.

This is not different from the common idea of working for a 'better' future, or indeed, as referring to Egyptian efforts in collaborating with other African countries for a 'brighter' future for the continent. In such case the interpreter may simply echo the trope used and say in Arabic (نعمل من أجل مستقبل مشرق), disregarding the comparative form of the English epithet. Even if the translator opted for the equivalent in Arabic that is (من أجل مستقبل أكثر إشراقاً), the meaning will hardly be more precise. 'Brighter' can certainly imply the Arabic 'مشرق' but 'مشرق' can mean 'luminous', (وضاء/ منير), 'brilliant' (يزدهي), or if translated to specific fields (مزدهر/ أكثر ازدهاراً). If all such terms can be equated (up to a point) with convincing Arabic counterparts, the problems would be greatly reduced, but consider the following statement and its possible translations:

"The present government seeks to ensure the well-being of the last-paid workers in the Egyptian quarries sector, smooth out the difficulties they face in marketing their goods (mainly marble and alabaster), and streamline the current practices in this trade" (Al-ahram weekly).

The meaning looks clear enough, but what precisely is well-being? Enani's (مرشد المترجم) gives one or two possible 'equivalents' (اطمئنان/ رفاة) but neither of these, we say, is adequately satisfactory. The fact is that the writer deliberately chooses a word with a vague meaning, but which can be sufficiently impressive, so as to gratify the reader of the paper without even hoping to know exactly what practical steps the government may (or intend) to take. The

same may be of the modish word 'streamline'. Does it mean more than organize? Would the translator be wrong to say simply "to organize", or even "re-organize"?

This could be challenging for the translators to deal with, and to convey the meaning accurately. Therefore, the translator must pertain the balance, which could be done either by echoing the trope, leaving the ambiguity of the source term, or by finding an equivalent that will ensure the cultural context of the target language without changing the original political message.

So, we can say that such use of such language is strategic and deliberately vague, which would enable the politicians to connect with their audience without committing to specifics. Noam Chomsky stated "Language is a weapon. It's a tool for power. It can be used to deceive or to make us believe things that are false" (Chomsky 2011). This statement with the one mentioned earlier by Political scientist Murray Edelman saying that "political language is designed to make lies sound truthful ..." reflect the fact that political languages, and for sure by extension political speeches, is crafted to influence, or better to say 'manipulate' the audience's perception, rather than conveying tangible information, avoiding concrete promises or accountability.

Strategic Ambiguity of Political Language: Broad, Abstract, and Ambivalent Terms for Wider Impact

Political parlance is designed to sound profound without committing to specifics, which simply means to be too broad or general. Take for example a politician promising "peace", that is (السلام) in Arabic, such a term may refer to more than one meaning according to the interlocutor's perspective. Peace may imply to some the end of war; to others, it may refer to economic stability or a lack of social disputes. This flexibility makes "peace" not only a strong word but also non-specific one.

We may have a word such as 'Improvement' that is (تحسين) in Arabic. So, improving one's life or having a better life (تحسين حياة الشخص), refers to more than one meaning according to the speaker's perspective. So, it may refer to a new car, more money, a promotion... etc. So (تحسين) is a very general and abstract word with no specific semantic value.

These words are not only abstract but also intentionally ambiguous, allowing audiences to interpret them based on their individual beliefs or cultural expectations. Although this flexibility helps politicians reach a wider audience, it creates significant challenges for translators whose primary goal is to maintain the term's emotional impact and cultural relevance. Gabriel Recchia and Michael N. Jones in *The Semantic Richness of Abstract Concepts* claimed that:

Abstract concepts may be semantically impoverished, deriving their meaning primarily from their associations with other words... Alternatively, they may be no less semantically rich, but be more grounded in introspective simulations... or aspects of meaning related to their social/communicative function.

'Prosperity' is another broad and abstract example used by politicians "promising prosperity", without mentioning any specific details to what they actually mean and what are the steps they are going to take, so it may refer to the economic growth, or it may refer to the improvement of social services. The equivalent term in Arabic that is (الازدهار) may refer to a kind of overall well-being that includes social harmony, while the same word in English may have slightly different connotations. These subtleties might change the message's impact; therefore, translators must think about which parts to highlight or modify to fit the intended audience. Another problem found in some books which are strictly adhering to the terms of non-English-speaking thinkers and politicians, presenting these terms in English translations may not be as clear as the original English terms in each case, such as the use of the term (subjectivity that is "الذاتية" in Arabic) instead of "الذات". This replacement of the two terms was not used to differentiate between the noun "الذات" and the coined abstract noun "الذاتية", but this was done because some non-English-speaking Europeans have used such a term.

And as a translator, I often stop at coined abstract nouns, realizing that such terms spread too much in a way that made me want to change the morphological paradigm of them to ones that give the intended meaning, but I was reluctant to do so for the accuracy in conveying these writers' way of thinking along with their intended meaning.

It should be added that the freedom of the interpreter in translation and interpretation is very limited, as he is committed to the source text, with the ability to add a few words [between square brackets], when it is impossible to have the correct meaning without such words. It is also worth mentioning that the intended meanings of abstracts are not very clear but from the context, however a politician may not give explanations of such words depending on his target audience's eloquence. Sometimes a politician presents intentional ambiguity to allow the audience to come out in the sense that he wants.

These subtle differences may affect the message's main impact which would force the translators to consider which aspects of the term should be emphasized or adapted to present to the target audience. Political theorist George Orwell addressed this in *Politics and the English Language*, where he pointed out that "the great enemy of clear language is insincerity" (Orwell 2021). Orwell argued that politicians use vague language deliberately, which allows them to hide their actual intentions, and this is what he referred to as "nonsense words." As these words are used to create rapport with the audience, by evoking their emotions, rather than presenting any truths or facts. So, when a translator confronts such vagueness, they have to deal with it very carefully and they have to make a hard call, whether to maintain this vagueness or to clarify the message to the target audience.

When we examine political parlance, we can find another level of ambiguity emerges with ambivalent terms; referring to two meanings which can be opposite to each other. These terms can cause a challenge to the translator simply because they enable one phrase to connect with various audience segments, even if those segments understand it in opposing ways. For instance, the term 'reform' may refer to a positive change for some listeners, while others may see it a threat to their traditions or stability. This duality of meaning not only complicates the message for the audience, but also creates a dilemma for translators, who must decide how to convey the term in a way that gives both interpretations.

Another example of dual meaning terms used in political jargon is "security", as for some it refers to protection, safety, and stability, for others, especially those concerned with issues like government surveillance or personal freedoms, "security" can carry a more negative

connotation, referring to restrictions or control. This duality cause divisions in the lines of the target audience as some feel reassured while others feel worry, completely two contradictory feelings. This makes it a bit challenging and tricky for such term to be translated, as the translator in this case has to find a term or a phrase in the target language that would maintain this balance and give give both sides of “security” without changing its original meaning too far in one direction.

From Data to Discourse: Translating Statistical Persuasion in Political Communication

Politicians usually use figures and statistics to support their arguments, form public perceptions, and persuade their audience. The way these figures or numbers is presented and translated can significantly affect its clarity, credibility, moreover its persuasive power.

Figures are used to create an authenticated narrative, to evoke an emotional response, or even to obscure truths. In this section I will address how politicians use statics and numbers as tools of persuasion, in addition this part will present the challenges of translating these figures while maintaining their intended impact.

• Turning Raw Data into Persuasive Arguments

Politicians do not always provide statistics with full transparency, usually they use them in a way that would serve their interests and support their arguments and political agendas. For example, President Barack Obama’s statement on the unemployment rate during his time as a president shows how a simple number can be turned into a victory story: “The unemployment rate has fallen to 4.7%, the lowest in nearly a decade” (Obama 2017). Hearing this would absolutely seems like a clear success, however without any other additional context, such as the fact that this rate has been actually affected by a reduction in the labor force participation rate, or the fact that many part-time workers were not able to find full time jobs, this does not give the whole story. So the statistic provided in this case may deceive the audience suggesting that the job market status was better than it really was.

Thus rendering such figures should be handled with similar care as the previous issue, since the translator here may need to present additional information, absent in the original text, clarifying the reasons behind this rate such as saying:

”على الرغم من انخفاض معدل البطالة إلى 4.7٪، إلا أن معدل المشاركة في القوى العاملة لا يزال منخفضًا تاريخيًا”

In English this would be: “Although the unemployment rate has decreased to 4.7%, the labor force participation rate remains historically low”, in order to ensure the audience is not misled by the figure alone, and the translator is allowed to do so even if only between square brackets.

• Exaggerating or Downplaying Figures for Persuasion

Another famous tactic used frequently in political speeches is to present the statistics the support a politician’s position and at the same time downplaying other opponents’ statistics. An example of exaggeration can be seen by George Bush during the financial crisis at the

United States in 2008, when he said: "The government has approved a \$700 billion bailout to stabilize our financial system" (Bush 2008).

This massive figure should have reflected how serious the situation was back then and the government's commitment to recovery, however the statistic was given without addressing the controversial nature of the bailout or its long-term impact on the economy.

Translating such a number is not only about conveying the figure itself, but also the political implications behind it. In such a case the translator may choose to add a specific context as the following:

"هذا الرقم البالغ 700 مليار دولار الذي أنفقته الحكومة من أجل استقرار البنوك يعد من أكبر التدخلات المالية في تاريخ الولايات المتحدة، رغم أنه قوبل بجدل واسع بين الجمهور".

That is "This \$700 billion figure, which the government spent to stabilize the banks, is among the largest financial interventions in U.S. history, though it was met with considerable public debate".

• Vagueness and Ambiguity in Statistical Claims

Politicians often use vague or nonspecific figures or statistics to give the impression that they are widely supported, e.g. "Most Americans agree that healthcare costs are too high", How can we believe such a statement without having any information about who made the survey to assure this, how many people were surveyed, or what is the exact percentage, all of which can make such a phrase sound deceiving.

When translating this type of data we have two options; whether to maintain the ambiguity, or to address it indirectly.

• The Emotional Appeal of Statistics

Numbers are always used in political speeches for emotional appeals especially when addressing numbers of deaths or injuries. A moving example can be seen in President Obama's statement after the Sandy Hook Elementary School shooting: "The majority of those who died today were children—20 beautiful, little kids between the ages of 5 and 10 years old. They had their entire lives ahead of them: birthdays, graduations, weddings, and kids of their own" (Pienda 2012). This figure is used not only to present a fact, but as a powerful emotional appeal for gun control.

The translation of this has to echo the emotional effect of the number such as saying:

"غالبية الذين فقدناهم اليوم في هذه المأساة كانوا أطفالاً—20 طفلاً جميلاً، صغاراً تتراوح أعمارهم بين 5 و 10 سنوات. كانت أمامهم حياتهم بالكامل: أعياد ميلاد، تخرجت، حفلات زفاف، وأطفال كانوا سيحملون أساءهم في المستقبل".

This would make the statement more emotional and tragic.

Finally and at the end of this point I want to assure that translating statistical data and figures in the political discourse is not just a simple numerical exchange; it is like solving an equation that requires precise balance between three main points: clarity, context and emotional appeal.

Political leaders use numbers to create their own narratives which may reflect or distort the truth, and the way these numbers are presented often shapes these narratives. Translators must overcome these complexities, making sure that the original persuasive message is preserved, and at the same time the audience understands both the significance and the limitations of the figures presented.

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